

Principals' Managerial Competencies as Correlates of Administrative Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

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Abstract

The study examined principals' managerial competencies as correlates of administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study while two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study consist 8,187 teachers comprising 1,500 males and 6,687 females in 269 public secondary schools in the six education zones in Anambra State. The sample of 819 teachers was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising proportionate stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used for the study. Two instruments were used for data collection: Principals' Managerial Competencies Questionnaire (PMCQ) and Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ). The face validation was done using three experts. The reliability of the instrument was done using Cronbach Alpha technique and the average coefficients were established at 0.81 for PMCQ and 0.87 for PAEQ. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistical tool was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that principals' disciplinary and communication competencies have positive and significant relationship with principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study concluded that the principals apply managerial competencies for effective administration of public secondary schools in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the study recommended that the principals should apply disciplinary competencies through written caution as stated in school regulation and oral caution in disciplining erring teachers and seeking teachers' opinion to enhance school administration effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Keyword: Principals' managerial competencies, administrative effectiveness

Introduction

Education remains the crucial instrument for furnishing individuals with skills for self-reliance, inculcating right values and morals in them for harmonious co-existence with other members of the society. One of the levels of education is secondary schools. Secondary education is learning activities organized for students after a successful completion of basic education. It is the type of education which the students receive after basic education to acquire additional skills and knowledge that prepare them for higher studies in tertiary institutions. Ezeaku and Obi (2025) opined that secondary education is the post-basic education level that equips students with fundamental knowledge for further studies, specific skills for useful living and also to raise morally upright individuals to become responsible members of the society. The daily activities of a secondary school are managed by a principal. The principal is the person in charge of planning, organizing and overseeing the daily operation and smooth functioning of a secondary school. Effective principals are expected to promote administrative effectiveness in order to accomplish stated goals of the school.

Administrative effectiveness can be seen as the achievement of operative goals, capabilities, experiences, energy goals and value. Adinna and Okaforcha (2019) stated that administrative effectiveness is the satisfaction derived by members and subsequently the internal structure and operation of the organization. Onyekwelu (2024a) referred to administrative effectiveness to the ability of principals to carry out administrative tasks of coordinating both human and material resources available and using them systematically for the achievement of educational objectives. Ugwu and Okoye (2024) identified administrative effectiveness as a symbol of good administrative style, team work, morale or motivation of staff, good teaching, conducive social climate as well as maintenance of rules and regulations. Principal's ability to control and maintain school infrastructural facilities, initiate good projects and complete both new ones and also those abandoned by his predecessors is exemplary of effectiveness.

Administrative effectiveness involves efforts and technical skills directed towards organizational tasks leading to goals achievement. Manafa and Adinna (2023) noted that principals must motivate staff to use their creativity and initiative as necessary inputs, towards the accomplishment of school goals. Okaforcha (2022) submitted that effective school administration as the successful attainment of predetermined educational objectives through utilization of the available resources. The smooth running and uninterrupted activities of any organization require high level of administrative effectiveness. Principals' effectiveness or ineffectiveness would determine the level of discipline or indiscipline among teachers, students and other members of staff. In this light, effective school principals are liked and respected, rather than feared. They communicate, care for students and are willing to impose punishment if necessary.

Contextually, administrative effectiveness operationally involves, among other things, coordinating both human and material resources available and using them systematically for the achievement of educational objectives. It denotes the ability of the principal to achieve the goals and objectives of the school. Hence, the school principal requires managerial competencies to smoothly run the daily affairs of secondary school.

Managerial competencies are the abilities to utilize the available resources to achieve desirable goals. Okaforcha and Nwabueze (2024) opted that competencies are the abilities required to effectively carry out a given task. It is the abilities to successfully carry out some set of activities or tasks to achieve set goals. Eziuzo et al. (2024) described managerial

competencies as the knowledge, skills and attitudes required for executing administrative tasks and activities. Similarly, Odu-Dikoro (2023) defined managerial competencies as the abilities of principals to skillfully and successfully plan, supervise, organize, co-ordinate, control, make decisions and initiate actions that would aid and encourage teachers to achieve school's set goals and objectives. Ukozor and Edet (2024) defined managerial competencies as the professional skills that could be applied by school principals to organize, coordinate, control and administer school human and materials resources to realize the school's objectives. Several scholars have highlighted several components of managerial competences. Obi et al. (2022) highlighted managerial competences to include communication competence, supervisory competency, disciplinary competency and motivational competency. In the same vein, Eziuzo et al. (2024) highlighted managerial competences to include: supervisory competency, disciplinary competency, communication competency, planning competency, decision-making competency, financial management competency and interpersonal relationships competency.

Managerial competencies are the abilities, thought processes and mentality expected to play out a task. Onyekwelu (2024c) stated that managerial competencies are the skills, knowledge and experience required for controlling the activities of others to attain desirable results. Katz as cited in Ugwu and Okoye (2024) expressed that managerial competencies includes discipline and relational abilities like correspondence, influences, designations and inspiration of work force (staff) in the school. They distinguished three managerial competencies abilities fundamental for management, in particular specialized human and applied. Specialized abilities includes the how principal might interpret the work and individuals who work under him, the human abilities include how much the head to interface with individuals while the applied abilities manages plan of thoughts and complex circumstances.

Contextually, principals' managerial competencies are the abilities of principals to properly direct and control the activities of teachers to achieve desirable results. It is the ability of the school principals to complete tasks using relevant skills and attitudes necessary to the job. Managerial skills and competencies contribute to a school's productivity, as they are necessary for managing staff toward achieving set school goals. The managerial competencies adopted for this study are: disciplinary and communication competencies because they are essential for performing core administrative duties in the school.

Principals' disciplinary competency is the basic knowledge that is considered necessary for a principal to acquire and to have a good command in the course of management of secondary schools. It is the principals' ability to discipline the erring teachers and students. However, discipline ideally means more than adhering to rules and regulations and entails the learner's ability to discern what is right or wrong (Ehiane, 2024). Discipline is widely acknowledged to be essential for creating a positive school climate conducive to sound academic performance (Sibomana & Andala, 2024). It is a basic requirement for successful teaching and learning in schools and a subject of concern for principals and teachers in schools (Edo & Bulopakaye, 2024). Principals' disciplinary competency should not be restricted to one approach; approaches such as corporal punishment, suspension, verbal punishment, withholding rewards and penalties can be used by principals as and when due. The competency of the principals as disciplinarians enable them to effectively perform the function of enforce the school rules effectively and overseeing the instructional activities of teachers and communicate their observations to them for possible modification in their teaching.

Communication is managerial competency required of school principal to ensure effective and timely exchange of information for the achievement of stated educational goals. Ikedimma et al. (2023) defined communication as the act of converging information, feelings, instruction, opinions, facts and advice accurately from one person to another or group of people. Communication means an exchange of information and messages between one or two individuals (Onyekwelu, 2024b). The principals as the chief administrators can apply communication competency to ensure smooth interactions and exchange of ideas in the school. Ughamadu et al. (2024) noted that communication competency related to skill and ability for disseminating information and understanding feelings or thoughts among persons. Ughamadu et al. added that if principals are fluent in communication competency, they will become successful in providing timely information that meets the needs and expectations of educational stakeholders. Communication competency includes verbal, non-verbal, listening and feedback competencies. The ability of the principal to communicate effectively is a gateway to good instructional leadership.

Sadly, this has not been the case in some public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is because it appears that some public secondary school principals do not adequately plan for their school programmes, do not apply appropriate managerial competencies of discipline, communication and instructional leadership and most important, the exclusion of staff in the school decision-making processes. It is further visible in cases of duplication of functions and general lack of direction in administration among school principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Furthermore, some secondary schools in Anambra State appear to be bedeviled with unpleasant incidences probably due to undesirable leadership behaviour of principals. Ibezim (2024) indicated series of principals' unhealthy or unethical behaviours such as being biased, refusing teachers to air their views on school affairs, favouritism and untimely dissemination of communication contradict the notion of authentic leadership practices in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Egboka and Onyeagba noted that the hostile, dishonest and unfriendly attitudes of some secondary school principals toward their teachers could demotivate them from performing additional roles that contribute to the attainment of educational objectives in Anambra State. The principals exhibiting undesirable behaviours which are considered inimical to effective administration cast doubts on their leadership practices, managerial competencies and financial management practices in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Such undesirable behaviours appear to include the display of hostile behaviour toward their subordinates, rebuking them in front of the students for little mistakes and rarely making out time to interact with them. Hence, some teachers seem to resort to gossiping their principals, showing poor work attitude, performing below their job expectation and possibly even develop the tendency of engaging in conflict that hinder effective school administration in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is based on the above problem that prompted the researcher to examine principals' managerial competencies and financial management practices as correlates of administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine principals' managerial competencies as correlates of administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent principals' disciplinary competency relate to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Find out the extent principals' communication competency relate to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does principals' disciplinary competency relate to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. To what extent does principals' communication competency relate to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Principals' disciplinary competency does not significantly relate to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Principals' communication competency does not significantly relate to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Method

The study was carried out in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study consist 8,187 teachers comprising 1,500 males and 6,687 females in 269 public secondary schools in the six education zones in Anambra State. The sample of 819 teachers (that is, 10% of teachers' population) was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising proportionate stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used for the study. Two instruments were used for data collection: Principals' Managerial Competencies Questionnaire (PMCQ) and Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ).The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. The face validation was done using three experts, two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation, all in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State. The reliability of the instrument was done using Cronbach Alpha technique and the average coefficients were established at 0.81 for PMCQ and 0.87 for PAEQ. Direct method of data administration was utilized by the researcher together with five research assistants. Out of 819copies of the instrument administered, 784 copies representing 96% of the instrument were correctly completed and returned. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistical tool was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Result

Research Question One: To what extent does principals' disciplinary competency relate to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between principals' disciplinary competency and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Variables	N	r	r ²	Remark
Principals' disciplinary competency	784	0.628	0.581	Moderately Positive
Administrative effectiveness	784			

***Significant at $p < 0.05$*

The summary result of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient on Table 1 showed that principals' disciplinary competency has a moderate positive relationship with administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This revealed a moderate positive correlation coefficient valued at 0.628 which indicated that there is a

moderate positive relationship existing between principals' disciplinary competency and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit increase in the application of principals' disciplinary competency in the school leads to 0.628 (63%) increases in administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State and vice versa. The coefficient of determination (r^2) value of 0.581 showed that the explanatory power of the variable was moderate. This implies that 58% of the variations in administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State were moderately accounted for by the variations in principals' disciplinary competency.

Research Question Two: To what extent does principals' communication competency relate to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between principals' disciplinary competency and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Variables	N	R	r^2	Remark
Principals' communication competency	784	0.772	0.732	Highly Positive
Administrative effectiveness	784			

***Significant at $p < 0.05$*

The summary result of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient on Table 2 showed that principals' communication competency has a high positive relationship with administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This revealed a high positive correlation coefficient valued at 0.772 which indicated that there is a high positive relationship existing between principals' communication competency and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit improvement in the application of principals' communication competency in the school leads to 0.772 (77%) improvement in administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State and vice versa. The coefficient of determination (r^2) value of 0.732 showed that the explanatory power of the variable was high. This implies that 73% of the variations in administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State were highly accounted for by the variations in principals' communication competency.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Principals' disciplinary competency does not significantly relate to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the significant relationship between principals' disciplinary competency and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Variables	N	r	r^2	p-value	Remark
Principals' disciplinary competency	784	0.628	0.581	0.000	Significant
Administrative effectiveness	784				

***Significant at $p < 0.05$*

The summary result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on Table 3 showed the significant relationship between principals' disciplinary competency and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State with p-value =

0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the study rejected the null hypothesis that principals' disciplinary competency does not significantly relates to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that principals' disciplinary competency significantly related to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Principals' communication competency does not significantly relate to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Table 4: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the significant relationship between principals' communication competency and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Variables	N	r	r ²	p-value	Remark
Principals' communication competency	784	0.772	0.732	0.000	Significant
Administrative effectiveness	784				

****Significant at $p < 0.05$**

The summary result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on Table 4 showed the significant relationship between principals' communication competency and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State with p-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the study rejected the null hypothesis that principals' communication competency does not significantly relates to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that principals' communication competency significantly related to administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

Findings on the extent of relationship between principals' disciplinary competency and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State indicated that principals' disciplinary competency has a moderate positive relationship valued at 0.628 with administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This means that increase in principals' disciplinary competency will bring about 63% increases in administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State and vice versa. The study also revealed that principals' disciplinary competency has a significant relationship with administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This result is in consonance with the findings of Onafowo et al. (2023) that revealed that principals' display of disciplinary competencies in the school are significantly related to teachers' work performance in terms of instructional delivery, attendance to classes and record keeping respectively. Similarly, Dunu (2023) findings revealed that principals give serious attention to issues concerning discipline in the school and monitor classroom co-curricular activities to keep teachers constructively occupied. Sibomana and Andala (2024) results showed that principals' practice of disciplinary competencies has positive and significant effect on teachers' productivity. Therefore, it is expected that as principals continue improving on their disciplinary competencies and leadership qualities, their administrative effectiveness on their assign tasks would continue to increase. This affirmed the finding of Ehiane (2024) which indicated that a positive relationship existed between principals' disciplinary competency and teachers' job performance in secondary schools. The similarities with the findings could be connected to the fact that the studies were conducted at secondary school level using teachers

as the participants. The principals' disciplinary competency is crucial for fostering a positive and productive school environment, as it directly impacts students and staff well-being, school climate and ultimately, students' achievement. It is also essential in overseeing the activities of teachers and rendering professional supports that could be responsible for the moderate positive relationship and guidelines for good administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. It is through disciplinary competency that principals keep track of problems encountered by teachers and promptly address the issues.

Findings on the extent of relationship between principals' communication competency and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State indicated that principals' communication competency has a high positive relationship valued at 0.772 with administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This means that increase in the application of principals' communication competency will bring about 77% increases in administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State and vice versa. The study also revealed that principals' communication competency has a significant relationship with administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This result is in consonance with the findings of Ikedimma et al. (2023) that the communication competencies of principals is exhibited through providing clarity in direction and setting performance expectations for teachers to enable them understand their responsibilities could account for the strong relationship with their job commitment in secondary schools. Ugwu and Okoye (2024) noted that the rapport and trust which could be established through communication competence create a comfortable work environment that enhances the job commitment of teachers. In line with the study, Ibezim (2024) findings indicated that the communication competencies of principals which make them approachable and willing to listen attentively to teachers create a feeling of being heard and valued which significantly correlates with their job commitment in public secondary schools. The findings of the study agreed with Obiekwe et al. (2024) who concluded that poor principals' competencies in the areas of planning, communication and delegation prevent effective job performance by teachers. Principals are required to communicate their ideas and plans about their school programmes to teachers to enable them to undertake their job effectively. A two-way communication system is required for both principals and teachers to facilitate teachers' job effectiveness. The finding is in line with Ughamadu et al. (2024) findings that through an effective communication system in school, teachers would be able to express themselves to the principals about their job assignments, working conditions and concerns regarding their professional growth. The similarities could be attributed to the fact that communication is part of the principal's administrative skill to establish a sound information network that keeps teachers informed about the progress and challenges facing a school.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concluded that the principals apply managerial competencies for effective administration of public secondary schools in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The managerial competencies are disciplinary and communication competencies that promote a positive school learning climate. The disciplinary and communication competencies are paramount if the objectives of secondary education are to be meaningfully translated into reality.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Principals should apply disciplinary competencies through written caution as stated in school regulation and oral caution in disciplining erring teachers and seeking

teachers' opinion to enhance school administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

2. Post Primary School Service Commission should organize annual professional development programme for principals to upgrade their communication competencies and continuously improve their knowledge about the barriers to communication, solutions to overcome these barriers, and better listening ability for effective school administration in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

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